

CHARACTERIZATION AND ASSESSMENT OF SURFACTIN AND SOYA-SAPONIN BIOCHEMICAL PESTICIDE ON THE QUALITY OF STORED MAIZE AND COWPEA GRAINS

Lasisi S. A¹, Bada, B. S¹, Shittu², O.B., Olatunde, K.A¹, Anjorin, T.S³

¹Department of Environmental Resources Management and Toxicology, College of Environmental Resources Management, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria

²Department of Microbiology, College of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria

³Department of Crop Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Abuja Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study developed and assessed the efficacy of surfactin and soya-saponins-based biochemical pesticides on the quality of maize and cowpea grains. The surfactin was produced from solid-state fermentation of yam peel and soya waste with *Bacillus subtilis*. The saponin was obtained from the water extract of soya bean. The two active ingredients in the formulation were produced and characterized using a Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR) spectrometer for structural identity and Spectrum lab 752s for quantification. The efficacy of the derived formulation in reducing weevil infestation in stored cowpea and maize grains was assessed. The peak at 1651.5 cm⁻¹ shown in Figure 3 confirms the presence of primary amide as –C=C- stretch vibrations for primary amide are usually observed in the region 1680-1640 cm⁻¹. Effects of the TFP2 (Surfactin + Soya-saponin at 20%), SCP (Lambda-cyhalothrin synthetic chemical pesticide), TM (ginger + pepper + garlic+neem and turmeric + neem + water extracts), and CN treatments on physical and quality parameters: moisture content, weevil infestation, moisture content, hundred seed weight, in 12-month storage in plastic containers, were evaluated. Moisture content increased in maize after 6 months' storage with TM and CN treatment by 2 and 2.3 %, respectively, while storage with TFP and SCP for 12 months led to 1.39 and 2.73% increase, respectively. Storage for 6 months with CN and TM in maize and cowpea resulted in 5 and 13 weevil detections, respectively. While no weevil was found in storage with TFP and SCP for 12 months Weevil infestation in both grains was controlled in 12 months of storage with the TFP resulting in no weevil detection in maize and cowpea, compared with 6 months of storage with TM and CN, where 5 and 13 dead weevils were detected.

Keywords: Solid-state fermentation, Characterization, surfactin, soya-saponin, maize weevils, cowpea weevils

INTRODUCTION

Environmental fate and long-term toxicity of synthetic chemicals have continued to attract attention due to their effects on human health and the environment. Similarly, increased consumers' awareness of the link between a safe food supply system and ecological processes that life depends on have sustained interest in the safe use of chemicals in food production. Safe and environment-friendly

alternatives such as botanicals and bio-molecules from micros are now preferred.

Despite the continuous emphasis on natural pest management, the use of phytochemical bio-pesticides continues to be < 1% of the total pesticide use (Walia *et al.*, 2017). A determined effort aimed at minimizing food losses appears more resource-efficient way to strengthen food security through improved crop productivity to sustainably combat

hunger and reduce pressure on agricultural land. The concerns over the persistence and residues of long-lasting synthetic chemicals have sustained the global efforts constantly made to develop natural alternatives to synthetic chemicals to achieve the same efficacy at a competitive cost.

Natural alternatives though, are not fast acting but pests take longer time to develop resistance to them as they have complex modes of action, in contrast to synthetic chemicals with simple modes of action, often related to a single gene, which enables pests to develop resistance more easily when used repeatedly. Wang *et al.* (2015) reported resistance levels in some pathogens associated with pepper and cucumber blight after 2-3 years of Metalaxyl applications. The entry of chemical pesticides into the food chain has disturbed the ecological balance of microbes inhabiting soil, leading to the development of resistant strains of pathogens, groundwater contamination and obvious health risks to humans (Meena and Kanwar, 2014).

Surfactin capacity to inhibit aflatoxin production by *Aspergillus spp.* (- cottonseed, peanuts and corn) on the field and storage (Rodriguez and Mahoney, 1994) has been demonstrated. Surfactin has exhibited bio-control of *Pectobacterium* and *Dickeya spp.* which cause soft rot (Krzyzanowska *et al.*, 2012). Saponins have also been shown to be effective against *Sclerotinia fructicola*, *Trichothecium roseum* and *Pyricularia oryzae*. Synthetic surfactants are usually used as major adjuvants in fungicides, insecticides and herbicide formulations where they act as emulsifying, dispersing, spreading and wetting agents to enhance the efficiency of pesticides.

Analysis or FTIR Spectroscopy, is an analytical technique used to identify organic, polymeric, and, in some cases, inorganic materials. Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) identifies chemical bonds in a

molecule by producing an infrared absorption spectrum (Intertek, 2019). The FTIR analysis method uses infrared light to scan test samples and observe chemical properties. Alterations in the characteristic pattern of absorption bands indicate a change in the material composition (Intertek, 2019). FTIR is useful in identifying and characterizing unknown materials, detecting contaminants in a material, finding additives, and identifying decomposition and oxidation.

This study attempted to produce and characterize surfactin from solid-state fermentation of yam peel and determine the quality characteristic of soya-saponin water extract. The effects of surfactin and soya-saponin-based formulation on the quality of stored maize and cowpea were also examined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Surfactin and soya-saponin production

For the surfactin production, a preliminary screening was carried out to determine the hemolytic properties of the *Bacillus* strain by plating on chocolate agar at 37°C for 48 hours and stored at 4°C until use at the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital's Medical Laboratory Department. Two loops of grown bacterial cells were sub-cultured on a 50 ml nutrient broth for another 24 h and used immediately as inoculums. In 500 ml conical flasks, 20 g of purified yam peel powder with moisture content adjusted to 25% was autoclaved. The fermented mass was diluted with 60 ml of distilled water and centrifuged (Chalice Wagtech, Thatcham, England) at 6000 rpm for 30 minutes to remove the bacterial cells and other insoluble matter. Surfactin yield was estimated from the concentration of the filtrate using a UV-Spectrophotometer (Spectrum lab 752s, Guangzhou, China) with absorbance measured at 214nm, and applying Beer's Law.

For the soya-saponin extraction, the method described by Güçlü-Üstündağ and Giuseppe (2007) was adopted with some modifications. Five hundred grams of soybean purchased at Gwagwalada open market cleaned, washed, and oven dried at 50 °C for 24 hours. Thirty grams of the flour weighed into a 100 ml beaker containing 300 ml of distilled water only and stirred intermittently for 1 hour. The slurry was sieved with muslin cloth and the filtrate was left to stand refrigerated overnight.

Characterization of Surfactin

The test-purified surfactin sample was spotted on a nutrient agar plate in triplicates, and a mist of diesel oil was applied with an airbrush and incubated for 48 hours as described by Morikawa *et al.* (1993). The Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) of the test surfactin was determined using the method described by Chang *et al.* (1987) with some modifications. Different concentrations of the test-surfactin ranged from 0.0001, 0.0005, 0.001, and 0.0015 to 0.005 % (v/v) prepared with the boiled distilled water and turbidity read three times with LaMotte Smart 3 Colorimeter.

FTIR spectrum for the structural chemistry of surfactin produced using FTIR Nicolet Is50 Spectrometer at the laboratory of Africa University of Science and Technology, Abuja, Nigeria. *Characterization of soya-saponin*: One millilitre of test saponin was diluted with 1 ml of water and shaken vigorously at room temperature as described by Astuti (2011). Stable froth observed after 30 minutes indicated the presence of saponins (Wijanarko *et al.*, 2017). Liebermann Burchard (LB) reagent consisted of anhydrate acetic acid and concentrated sulfuric acid. Sample identification was done by adding the sample, acetic acid, and sulfuric acid in the ratio of 5:5:3 (Wijanarko *et al.*, 2017).

Biopesticide formulation

The active ingredients; surfactin and soya-

saponin in ratio 1:1 constitute 15% of biopesticide formulation designated as TFP1. TFP2 represents an active ingredient constituting 20% of the formulation. The percentages of the inert material were 80 and 85% for TFP1 and TFP2 (1600ml/ha), respectively. Lambda-cyhalothrin, a synthetic pyrethroid pesticide (SCP) (400ml/ha) used as a positive control in this current study.

Grain storage experiment

The method described by Chattha *et al.* (2018) was adopted for monitoring the moisture content. This involved oven-drying at 105 °C for 24 h after sorting and grading and only grains unbroken were used for further investigation. For 100 seed weights, the method described by Brasil (2009) was adopted with some modifications. The 100 seeds were counted and weighed on the Petri dish. The values obtained were an average of three replicates. The method of seed vigour testing (ISTA, 2011); fifty seeds in each treatment were weighed and placed in a 150 ml distilled water-containing beaker. Beakers are sealed with aluminium foil and kept for 24 hours. For the determination of insect infestation, the methods described by Utono (2013) were used with some modifications as fifty grams of the samples weighed into a sieve (of about 3mm) with larval, pupa and adult stages of insect counted.

Statistical analysis

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out on data sets obtained to determine the significant difference among parameters assessed to determine the effects of formulated biopesticide in the control of field and post-harvest losses in maize and cowpea.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plate 1 depicts the haemolysis by *Bacillus subtilis* sub-cultured on chocolate agar. The

results obtained from substrates preliminarily exploited for cheap surfactin production are shown in Figure 1. Purified surfactin yield from yam peel powder at 25% moisture level gave a concentrate on of 4.76 mg/l with UV spectrophotometric measurement using Beer's law to quantify the output. Zanotto *et*

al. (2019) reported 3.26 mg/gds for rice straw + rapeseed meal, 6.25 mg/gds for rice straw + soybean four; 3.47 mg/gds for rice straw + wheat bran, and 15.17 mg/gds for rice straw +soybean flour + glycerol.

Plate 1: *Bacillus subtilis* sub-cultured in chocolate agar

Characterization of surfactin

Halo formation in the plates confirms the surface activity of the test sample as shown in Plate 2.

YP = yam peel, SW=soya waste, Supl = yeast

Figure 1: Production of Surfactin from different crop produce substrates at different moisture levels

Plate 2: Halo formation on nutrient agar

Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) determination of surfactin

Absorption value of 0.18 at 214 nm and molar extinction coefficient value of 923 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for peptide bond (Kuipers and Grupen, 2007) gave a CMC value of 19.5 μmol/l with 56 % purity level. CMC, purity level and yield for saponins are not generally stated, even for standard because of differences in processing method; part of plant used; genetic origin; the environmental and agronomic factors

associated with growth of the plant, and post-harvest treatments such as storage and processing (Fenwick *et al.*, 1991). The plot of turbidity (NTU) against concentration (% v/v) is an indication that the CMC value for surfactin was well below 0.001% as shown in Figure 2. Some qualitative characteristic tests such as the froth and Libermann test were carried out on the extracted soya-saponin as shown in plates 3 and 4.

Figure 2: CMC determination for surfactin

Plate 3: Froth test for saponin

Plate 4: Libermann saponin test

FTIR Spectra: In FTIR spectra, peptide-bond is a marker group for lipopeptide (Cheng *et al.*, 2012). The peak at 1651.5 cm⁻¹ shown in Figure 3 confirms the presence of primary amide as -C=O - stretch vibrations for primary amide are usually observed in the region 1680-1640 cm⁻¹. The N-H stretching vibrations observed at 3479.90 cm⁻¹ confirm the compound to be an aliphatic primary amide.

The N-H stretching vibrations for aliphatic primary amides are generally observed between 3500- 3100 cm⁻¹ with two bands due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes. The C-N stretching vibration of the aliphatic primary amide appeared in the fingerprint region at 1025cm⁻¹ and the N-H bending vibration for the amide was observed at 632.40 cm⁻¹ as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: FTIR Spectra of the Surfactin produced from *Bacillus subtilis*

Figure 4: FTIR Spectra showing the different absorption peaks for Surfactin produced *Bacillus subtilis* strain, nutritional and the environmental conditions.

Table 3: Quality characteristics of stored maize with four storage duration

Parameter	Storage Duration (months)			
	Initial	3months	6months	9months
12months				
		<i>Moisture content (%)</i>		
TM	13.32 ^d	13.45 ^c	13.72 ^c	13.52 ^b
TFP	13.46 ^a	13.53 ^a	13.59 ^e	13.63 ^a
SCP	13.15 ^{bcd}	13.37 ^{abc}	13.39 ^{bdf}	13.49 ^{ab}
CN	13.33 ^c	13.52 ^b	13.84 ^a	
		<i>Insect infestation</i>		
TM	0	5	13	
TFP	0	0	0	
SCP	0	0	0	
CN	0	10	0	
		<i>Weight of 100 seeds (g)</i>		
TM	14.53 ^b	14.34 ^c	12.48 ^e	11.75 ^e
TFP	14.36 ^c	14.36 ^b	14.33 ^a	14.18 ^a
SCP	14.35 ^{abc}	14.23 ^{abc}	14.12 ^c	4.07 ^c
CN	14.62 ^a	13.45 ^a	11.01 ^{bde}	9.04 ^{bdf}

The values in the same column with the same superscript letters are not statistically different by DMRT.

CONCLUSION

It is confirmed that some crop-produce wastes such as yam peel and soya waste, are cheap and avoidable materials for the production of biomolecules used as active ingredients in the biochemical pesticide formulation. The characterization confirmed that the biomolecules obtained from solid-state fermentation of yam peel and water extraction of saponins were chemically and structurally identical to standards.

The TFP and were comparable in the effective control of increased moisture, which predisposes grains to fungi infestation during storage. Weevil infestation in both grains was controlled in 12 months of storage with the TFP resulting in no weevil's detection in maize and cowpea, compared with 6 months storage with TM and CN, where 5 and 6 dead weevils were detected.

REFERENCES

- Astuti, S. M., Mimi, S. A. M., Retno, A. M., and Awalludin, R. (2011). Determination of Saponin Compound from *Anredera cordifolia* (Ten) Steenis Plant (Binahong) to Potential Treatment for Several Diseases. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 3 (4): 224-232
- Brasil, I. (2009). Regras para Análise de Sementes. 1st edn. Ministério da Agricultura, Pecuária Abastecimento, Brasília. 396 p.
- Chang, C Y., Wang, S.J., Liu, I, J.Y. and Chiu, Y. C. (1987). A simple method for determining the critical micelle concentration of surfactant. *Journal of the Chinese Society of Chemical Society*, 34 (3) 243-246.
- Chattha, S.H, Hasfalina, C. M., Mirani, B. N., Mahadi, M. R and Lee, T. S. (2016). Food grain losses associated with indigenous storage methods and development of storage facilities for food security: *International Food Research Journal* 23:57-63.
- Cheng C, Wang JN, Xu L, Li AM (2012) Preparation of new hyper cross-linked chelating resin for adsorption of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ from water. *Chinese Chemical Letters* 23: 245–248.
- Dubale, B., Waktole, S., Solomon, A., Geremew, B. and Sethu, M. R. (2012). Influence of Agro-Ecologies, Traditional Storage Containers and Major Insect Pests on Stored Maize (*Zea mays* L.) in Selected Woredas of Jimma Zone. *Asian J. Plant Science*, 11: 226-234.
- FAOSTAT (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Statistics) (2015). Country/Territorial Notes. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Statistics Division. <http://faostat3.fao.org/download/R/RP/E> (Accessed August 8, 2020)
- Fenwick, G. R., Price, K. R., Tsukamoto, C., and Okubo, K. (1991). Saponins. In: J.P.F. Güçlü-Üstündağ, Ö. and Mazza, G. (2007). Saponins: Properties, Applications and Processing. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* 47: 231-58.
- Kuipers, B. J. and Gruppen H. (2007). Prediction of molar extinction coefficients of proteins and peptides using UV absorption of the constituent amino acids at 214 nm to enable quantitative reverse phase high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis. *Journal Agriculture Food Chemistry* 55 (14):5445-51.
- Meena, Khem R. and Kanwar, Shamsher S. (2014). Lipopeptides as the Antifungal and Antibacterial Agents: Applications in Food Safety and Therapeutics. Hindawi Publishing Corporation BioMed Research International Article ID 473050
- Morikawa, M., Daido, H., Takao, T., Murata, S., Shimonishi, Y. and Imanaka, T.(1993). A new lipopeptide biosurfactant produced by *Arthrobacter sp.* strain MIS38. *J. Bacteriol*, 175, 6459–6466.
- National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services (NAERLS) (2010). Annual report 2010. Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. <https://orr.naerls.gov.ng/search?page=5&rdr=1>. (Accessed 5/7/2020)
- National Programme for Agriculture and Food Security, (2010). Report of the 2009 Agricultural Production Survey. Abuja, Nigeria, pp. 86
- Rodriguez, S. B. and Mahoney N. E. (1994). Inhibition of aflatoxin production by surfactants. *Applied Environmental Microbiology* 60:106–110.
- Utono, I. (2013). A survey of systems of grain storage and management of insect pests in stored grain in Kebbi state. *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 3: 51-61
-

- Walia, S., Saha, S. and Tripathi, V. (2017). Phytochemical biopesticides: some recent developments. *Phytochemical Review* 16, 989–1007.
- Walter, V., Syldatk, C. and Hausmann, R. (2010). Screening Concepts for the Isolation of Biosurfactant Producing Microorganisms. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*. 672: 1-13.
- Wang, F., Zhu, L., Wang, X., Wang, J. and Wang, J., (2015). Impact of repeated applications of metalaxyl on its dissipation and microbial community in soil. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* 226 (12):.1-14.
- Wijanarko, A., Ginting, M. J., Sahlan, M., Savitri, M. K. E., Florensia, Y., Sudiarta, M. R., Satria Pastika, S., Rafiki, F. and Hermansyah, H. (2017). Saponini isolation is Main Ingredients of insecticide and collagen type I from the crown of Thorn–Starfish (*Acanthaster planci*). IOP Conf. Series: *Earth and Environmental Science*, 89 012032
- Zanotto, A. W., Valério, A., and de Andrade, C. J. (2019). New sustainable alternatives to reduce the production costs for surfactin 50 years after the discovery. *Applied Microbiol Biotechnology* 103, 8647–8656.
-